

Studies in Terpenes. Part XII. Transformations of Some Terpenoids with Chloranil

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Transformations of various terpenoids under the influence of chloranil have been examined. (+)-Limonene gives rise to ($\pm$)-limonene, α -terpinene, *p*-menthene, and *p*-cymene; 3-carene, α -terpinene, terpinolene (?), *m*-isomers, menthene, *p*- and *m*-cymenes; β -pinene, α -pinene, bornyl chloride, camphene, and α -terpinene; α -pinene, bornyl chloride and camphene; and bornyl chloride, camphene. Camphene refuses to be affected by chloranil. Thus chloranil can cause isomerisation including racemisation, aromatisation, hydrogen transfer, hydrochlorination and dehydrochlorination. A mechanism is proposed to account for the formation of the reaction products.

Although reactions of chloranil with different types of hydrocarbons have been investigated¹⁻³, reports of corresponding reactions with terpenoids are notably rare^{4,5}. We therefore undertook a detailed investigation of the transformations of a number of terpenoids with chloranil.

(+)-Limonene (I), when refluxed with chloranil, yielded a mixture of hydrocarbons composed of ($\pm$)-limonene, α -terpinene (IV), *p*-menthene, and *p*-cymene.

The action of chloranil on 3-carene (V) gave rise to α -terpinene, terpinolene (?), *m*-isomers answering Wallach's colour test^{6,7}, menthene, and *p*- and *m*-cymenes.

β -Pinene (VI) reacted rapidly with chloranil to give a product consisting of α -pinene (VII), bornyl chloride (IX), camphene (XI), and α -terpinene. Unlike the β -isomer, α -pinene offered some resistance to the action of chloranil at 160-70°. Repeated processing with the quinone, however, gave rise to bornyl chloride and camphene. Only traces of cymenes (*p*- and *o*-) were found among the reaction products of β - and α -pinenes.

Dehydrochlorination was found to take place when bornyl chloride was heated with chloranil, resulting in camphene. On the other hand, camphene remained unchanged on treatment with chloranil.

In all cases with (+)-limonene, 3-carene, and α - and β -pinenes, tetrachlorohydroquinone was obtained. Further, hydrogen chloride was given off slowly in all reactions, except in the reaction of α -pinene at 160-70° and of camphene.

1. Arnold and Collins, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 1407.
2. Arnold *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1941, 62, 963.
3. Dost and Nes, *Rev. trav. Chim.*, 1951, 70, 403.
4. Fujita and Ohashi, *J. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1942, 63, 1443; *Chem. Abs.*, 1947, 41, 3175.
5. Verghese, *this Journal*, 1959, 36, 151.
6. Wallach, *Annalen*, 1887, 239, 1.
7. Bardyshev, *Doklady Akad. Nauk. SSSR*, 1953, 20 (6), 1035.

From the foregoing experimental results it emerges that in addition to dehydrogenative action, chloranil can effect isomerisation, hydrogen transfer, ~~hydrochlorination~~, and dehydrochlorination.

The rearrangements of the terpene hydrocarbons, brought about by chloranil, can be classified into groups according to the overall stoichiometric results. (+)-Limonene gave rise to other *p*-menthadienes by migration of the exterior double bond; 3-carene, *p*- and *m*-menthadienes by two-directional cleavage of the three-membered system; α - and β -pinenes, *p*-menthadienes by decyclisation of the cyclobutane ring and camphene, by change of ring structure. Also, in keeping with the superior reactivity of hydrocarbons with exo double bond to a cyclohexane ring, β -pinene is found to be more reactive than the α -isomer⁸. A special case of isomerisation is the racemisation of (+)-limonene.

Whereas hydrogen transfer between terpene hydrocarbons and chloranil has taken place, as shown by the formation of tetrachlorohydroquinone, it is interesting to note that hydrogen-transfer has occurred between the hydrocarbons, leading to menthenes and cymenes.

A rather unexpected property of chloranil, viz., hydrochlorination, is found in the production of bornyl chloride from α - and β -pinenes, a conversion hitherto known to take place at low temperatures⁹. Although the other terpenes examined are capable of adding the elements of hydrogen chloride¹⁰, under the present experimental conditions, these have escaped this process.

Moreover, for the first time, the dehydro halogenation property of chloranil has been observed in the conversion of bornyl chloride into camphene.

Certain observations may be made concerning the relative reactivities of the terpenoids to aromatisation. The ability to undergo conversion to cymenes is of the order: (+)-limonene and 3-carene > α - and β -pinenes > camphene and bornyl chloride. (+)-Limonene furnished *p*-cymene; 3-carene, *p*- and *m*-cymenes; α - and β -pinenes, *p*- and *o*-cymenes (in very poor yields); and bornyl chloride and camphene, none. In other words, terpenoids belonging to the *p*-menthane, carene, pinane, and camphane series respond differently towards chloranil. Although α - and β -pinenes have isomerised to *p*-menthadienes (and perhaps to *o*-menthadienes), which can further be dehydrogenated to cymenes, it is seen that the sequence of reactions leading to camphene and bornyl chloride has effectively blocked and superseded the aromatisation step, so much so, that cymenes are formed only in extremely poor amounts. Hence, dehydrogenation by refluxing the terpenoid with chloranil is unsuitable for structural evaluation due to the danger of skeletal alteration, which can either vitiate the dehydrogenation step or lead to wrong conclusions.

We are investigating further the transformations of a large variety of terpenoids to establish firmly these new properties of chloranil and also to develop suitable dehydrogenation procedure which may offset some of the undesirable side-reactions.

8. Brown *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 467; Brown, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, 22, 439; Fleck, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, 22, 430. Cf. Austerweil, *Perf. Essent. Oil Rec.*, 1925, 17, 187.

9. Acharya and Wheeler, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1934, 3, Part II, 163.

10. Walach, *Annalen*, 1898, 245, 241; 1892, 270, 171; Aschan, *ibid.*, 1930, 461, 1; Krestinski and Golovaskaya, *J. Appl. Chem., USSR*, 1939, 12, 878. For other references, see Simonsen, "Terpenes", Vol. II, Cambridge University Press, 2nd ed., 1953, pp. 159, 217.

Mechanism

Though we do not exclude the operation of a free radical mechanism¹¹, the results obtained can be accounted for by postulating carbonium ions as primary reaction intermediates. It is well known that chlorine atoms in 2 and 5 positions in the quinone are highly labile^{11,12}. This allows us, in the reactions under consideration, to look upon the liberation of hydrogen chloride as due to substitution either of the chlorine atoms of the chloranil or of reactive hydrogen atoms of the hydrocarbons, the other possibility being the splitting off of hydrogen chloride from initially formed addition products¹². The formation of several reaction products is as a consequence of the intervention of the H⁺ derived from the halogen acid.

Thus, the addition of proton to (+)-limonene furnishes the ion (II). This can revert to (+) or (-)-limonene with equal probability and accounts for dipentene formation. Alternatively, anhydride-ion shift in (II) leads to (III), which by proton elimination affords α -terpinene. Terpinolene is found in trace amounts, the reason being the predominant deactivation of (II) and (III) *via* the paths just mentioned¹³. It is noteworthy that α -terpinene, which is a major reaction product after a single processing of (+)-limonene with chloranil, is completely consumed later. Apparently, (+)-limonene is dehydrogenated to *p*-cymene through α -terpinene, although the participation of the other *p*-menthadienes is not entirely ruled out. That hydrogen transfer has taken place from *p*-menthadienes to chloranil leading to *p*-cymene is conclusively shown by the isolation of tetrachloro-hydroquinone.

Another route by which *p*-cymene can be formed involves hydrogen-transfer reactions as indicated by the general equation¹⁴:

This is supported by the positive Ipatieff-Pines test¹⁵ for mono-olefins on the final dehydrogenate obtained in the (+)-limonene runs.

Excluding the initial isomerisation of 3- to 4-carene⁵, the decyclisation of 3-carene with uptake of H⁺ gives rise to two types of carbonium ions, viz., *p*-menthenyl (II) and *m*-menthenyl (XII), which are responsible for *p*- and *m*-menthadienes¹⁶. The mechanism earlier advanced for the formation of *p*-cymene from (+)-limonene is also applicable to 3-carene. Further, *m*-isomers detected by Wallach's colour test¹⁷ in the first dehydrogenate were not traceable in the final dehydrogenate. Clearly, then, *m*-cymene is formed *via* the *m*-menthadienes. It is to be emphasised that the dehydrogenation can also be conceived as a result of direct abstraction of hydrogen from reactive groups in 3-carene followed by a two-way cleavage of the cyclopropane ring¹⁷.

11. Whitmore, "Organic Chemistry", D. Van Nostrand Company, Inc., New York, 2nd ed., 1951, p. 688. Price "Mechanism of Reactions at Carbon-Carbon Double Bonds", Interscience Publ. Inc., New York, 1948, p. 87.
12. Butz, "Organic Reactions", Vol. V, John Wiley and Sons Inc., New York, p. 147.
13. Verghese, this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 260.
14. Ipatieff and Pines, U.S.P. 2,431,756 and 2,420,749/ 1947; Ipatieff *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 604.
15. *ibid.*, 1952, 74, 4872.
16. Verghese, *et al.*, *J. Sci. Res.*, 1957, 16, 363.
17. Menon, *J. Madras Univ.*, 1953, 23, 92.

A. for α - and β -pinenes, addition of H^+ yields the C^+ ion (VIII) which is a resonance hybrid of the two extreme canonical forms (A) and (B). The ion (A) affords α -pinene by expulsion of H^+ , as noted in the β -pinene reaction. *p*-Menthenyl ion (II), the behaviour of which we discussed earlier, is obtained by a β -fission reaction of (A). Bornyl chloride (IX) results by the acquisition of a Cl^- ion by (B). The formation of (IX) in preference to isobornyl chloride and camphene hydrochloride is justified because it is the stablest of the chlorides^{18,19}. Further, (B) can suffer a β -bond migration to provide the camphanlyl ion (X) which is responsible for camphene. In case where camphene has been found, it is still an open question whether it is to be regarded as a direct isomerisation product or it has been formed by dehydrohalogenation of bornyl chloride.

Camphene formation from bornyl chloride can be assumed to proceed by an initial ionisation thus:

The bornyl ion $C_{10}H_{17}^+$ furnishes camphene with release of H^+ and the $(C_6O_2Cl_3)^-$ ion suffers decomposition to $C_6O_2Cl_4$ and Cl^- .

Finally, camphene is quite stable under the experimental conditions. Thus it cannot be an intermediate product either in the isomerisation or hydrochlorination step.

* EXPERIMENTAL

(+)-Limonene from Eastman Kodak Co. was steam distilled after basification with 10% NaOH solution, dried over Drierite, and then fractionated in Todd Precise Fractionation Assembly using 90cm/25 mm column packed with single turn glass helices at a reflux ratio of 25:1. The (+)-limonene was collected at 175-76°/737 mm; n_D^{20} 1.4731, d_4^{25} 0.8378, $[\alpha]_D^{30} +105.2^\circ$.

β -Pinene, separated from a commercial sample (Norda) in a manner described for (+)-limonene, had the following constants: b.p. 163-64°/738mm, n_D^{20} 1.4788, d_4^{20} 0.8721, $[\alpha]_D^{30} -19.5^\circ$.

α -Pinene isolated from a commercial sample (Crosby) had the following constants: b.p. 155-56°/738mm; n_D^{20} 1.4658, d_4^{20} 0.8595, $[\alpha]_D^{30} +27.36^\circ$.

Bornyl chloride, of m. p. 131° was prepared following the procedure of Acharya and Wheeler⁹. Camphene, obtained from Eastman Kodak Co., was purified by distillation from sodium, m.p. 50°. Chloranil (Eastman Kodak Co.) was used as such; m.p. 290-91°.

18. Huckel, "Theoretical Principles of Organic Chemistry", Elsevier Publ. Co., New York, 1955, Vol. I, p. 414.

19. Brooks, "The Chemistry of the Nonbenzenoid Hydrocarbons", Reinhold. Publ. Co., 1950, p. 546.

* The yields of oils reported are after drying over Drierite. Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Unless otherwise stated, all fractionations are done in Todd Precise Fractionation Assembly using 90 cm/5mm column packed with Monel spiral at a reflux ratio of 50:1.

General Reactions of Terpenoids with Chloranil

The individual conditions for the reactions of terpenoids and chloranil are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I
Reactions of chloranil with terpenoids.

Reaction No.	Reactants.		Temp.	Steam distillate.				
	Terpenoids.	Chloranil.		Oil.		Solid.		
	Kind	Wt.	Wt.	Yield.	n_D^{20} .	Wt.		
I (a)	(+)-Limonene	136.2 g.	49.2 g.	180-85°	82 g. (A)	1.4838	Nil	
	(b)	(A)	68.0	25.2	"	48 (B)	1.4818	Nil
	(c)	(B)	34.0	12.6	"	30 (C)	1.4832	Nil
	(d)	(C)	26.0	9.6	"	23 (D)	1.4863	Nil
	(e)	(D)	21.0	7.6	"	18 (E)	1.4878	Nil
II (a)	3-Carene	136.2	49.2	170-75°	85 (A)	1.4905	Nil	
	(b)	(A)	77.0	28.5	"	47 (B)	1.4831	Nil
	(c)	(B)	49.0	15.8	"	37 (C)	1.4843	Nil
	(d)	(C)	34.0	12.5	"	31 (D)	1.4870	Nil
	(e)	(D)	30.0	11.1	"	26 (E)	1.4890	Nil
III (a)	β -Pinene	136.2	49.2	170-80°	102 (A)	1.4764	Nil	
	(b)	(A)	85.0	31.6	"	60 (B)	1.4769	Nil
	(c)	(B)	51.0	19.0	"	47 (C)	1.4776	Nil
	(d)	(C)	43.0	15.8	"	38 (D)	1.4775	1.0 g.
	(e)	(D)	34.0	12.6	"	15 (E)	"	10
IV (a)	α -Pinene	136.2	49.2	160-70°	109 (A)	1.4731	Nil	
	(b)	(A)	106.0	38.0	170-90°	91 (B)	1.4750	Nil
	(c)	(B)	85.0	30.4	"	70 (C)	1.4760	Nil
	(d)	(C)	64.0	23.0	"	56 (D)	1.4753	Nil
	(e)	(D)	51.0	19.0	"	43 (E)	1.4798	Nil
V (a)	Bornyl chloride	29.0	8.4	180-90°	..	..	22 g.(A)	
VI (a)	Camphene	34.0	12.6	160-65°	..	..	27 (A)	
	(b)	(A)	24.0	6.7	"	..	..	19 (B)
	(c)	(B)	14.0	5.1	"	..	..	10 (C)
	(d)	(C)	6.5	2.4	"	..	..	5 (D)
	(e)	(D)	4.0	1.5	"	..	..	2.5(E)

In general, the reaction was carried out by heating on a Glas-Col heating mantle a mixture of the terpenoid and chloranil, taken in a two-necked flask fitted with a thermometer and a condenser, precautions having been taken to exclude moisture. After a period, the reaction mixture was cooled, basified with 10% NaOH solution, and steam distilled. The steam distillate, if oil, was dried over Drierite, and, if solid, was distilled from sodium and then either analysed or used in subsequent reactions.

Reaction (I). (+)-Limonene and Chloranil

Oil (A) (15g.) obtained in reaction I (a) had the following boiling ranges at 737mm: (1) up to 175°C: 25%, n_D^{20} 1.4680; (2) 171-73°: 25%, n_D^{20} 1.4755; (3) 173-75°: 20%, n_D^{20} 1.4815; (4) 175-73°: 20%, n_D^{20} 1.4852; (5) residue, steam distilled: 10%, n_D^{20} 1.5011.

Nitrosite.—Following the procedure earlier developed²⁰, from fractions (2), (3), (850 mg. each) about 250, 220, and 30 mg. respectively of a crystalline solid, melting at 155°, was obtained; a mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of α -terpinene nitrosite was undepressed.

Tetrabromide.— α -Terpinene present in fraction (3) (2.2 g.) was stripped off as nitrosite and the residual oil (680 mg.), when brominated²¹, afforded crystalline tetrabromide melting at 125° alone and in admixture with dipentene tetrabromide.

p-Cymene.—From a portion of fraction (4) (1.7 g.) after processing with 80% H₂SO₄²¹ and then with cold conc. sulphuric acid²³, about 850 mg. of a saturated oil (n_D^{20} 1.4906) was obtained. *p*-Cymene in this oil, according to the method of Leo *et al.*²², amounted to 92.7%.

Terpinolene was detected in fraction (3) by the transient purple coloration given in Wallach's test with acetic anhydride and sulphuric acid²³. All attempts to prepare a tetrabromide from this oil met with failure.

Oil E: Mono-olefins.—Ipatieff-Pines test¹⁵ for mono-olefins on this oil was positive.

α -Terpinene could not be identified in the oil. Moreover, the oil was recovered quantitatively on interaction with maleic anhydride on the lines recommended by Rudakov *et al.*²⁴ for α -terpinene.

p-Cymene.—A portion of the oil (3.4 g.) was depleted of the unsaturates by agitation with sulphuric acid^{21,23} and the usual work-up afforded pure *p*-cymene (2.6 g.), b.p. 177°/760 mm; n_D^{20} 1.4914.

Reaction (II). 3-Carene and Chloranil

Oil A (21 g.) of reaction II(a) distilled as follows at 740 mm: (1) up to 170°: 8%, n_D^{20} 1.4780; (2) 170-74°: 18%, n_D^{20} 1.4808; (3) 174-80°: 10%, n_D^{20} 1.4853; (4) 180-84°: 20%, n_D^{20} 1.4875; (5) 184-85°: 12%, n_D^{20} 1.4965; (6) residue, steam distilled: 12%, n_D^{20} 1.4975.

Fraction (2) (2.5 g.) yielded a crystalline product which corresponded to that of α -terpinene nitrosite; yield 750 mg, m.p. and mixed m.p. 155°. Fraction (3) (850 mg.) yielded only a few mg. of α -terpinene nitrosite.

Fractions (4) and (5) were brominated²¹; the former (1.5 g.) afforded only a few mg. of *trans*-terpinene tetrabromide, m.p. and mixed m. p. 116°; the latter failed to furnish any solid bromide.

As regards *m*-menthadienes, Wallach's test^{6,7} gave the following colours: Fractions (2 and 3), light blue; fraction (4), blue; fraction (5), intense methylene blue, indicating respectively the presence of isosylvestrene, sylvestrene, and sylve-terpinolene.

20. Sugathan and Verghese (unpublished).

21. Verghese and Yeddanapalli, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1953, 12, 121.

22. Xavier *et al.*, *Curr. Sci.*, 1953, 22, 112.

23. Henry and Paget, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 25.

24. Zhur. Obshch. Khim, 1954, 24, 1452.

Conjugated dienes were absent in oil (E) as shown by maleic anhydride inter-^{action}²⁴. The oil in the Ipatieff-Pines test¹⁵ gave, however, positive indication of me^{...}

By sulphuric acid processing^{21, 15} it was found that 85% of (E) was composed of saturated hydrocarbons (b.p. 175-76°/740mm, n_D^{20} 1.4921) with 43% *p*-cymene and ^{...}, *m*-cymene according to the method of Leo *et al*²².

Reaction III. β -Pinene and Chloranil

Oil A (19g.) of reaction (II) (a) distilled as follows at 736mm: (1) up to 155°: 8%, n_D^{20} 1.4643; (2) 155-56°: 56%, n_D^{20} 1.4680; (3) 156-69°: 16%, n_D^{20} 1.4801 (over 99.5% distilled at 168-69°); (4) residue, steam distilled: 8%, n_D^{20} 1.4841.

α -Pinene.—Employing the method of Mirov²⁵, fraction (2) (850mg.) yielded ($\pm$) α -pinene nitrosochloride (yield $\approx$ 50mg.), m.p. and mixed m.p.²⁶, 115°.

α -Terpinene nitrosite was prepared from 850mg. of fraction (2) (yield about 100 mg.). Fraction (3) did not furnish any α -terpinene nitrosite. No bromide could be obtained from any of the fractions.

Bornyl Chloride.—Oil (E) was magnetically stirred for 6 hrs. with 80% H₂SO₄ (36 ml). The reaction mixture was basified with 1% NaOH and on steam distillation gave a solid product (5g.). The combined solids from Reaction III (d-e) (16g.) were "purified" as for bornyl chloride following the directions of Acharya and Wheeler⁹, but the product (F), recovered almost quantitatively, showed an indefinite m.p. and contained chlorine. Solid (F) (2g.) was stirred successively with 6ml of cold 80% and 2ml of cold conc. sulphuric acid for 4 and 2 hrs. respectively, and after the usual work up furnished about 600 mg. of a solid. This on twice recrystallisation from aqueous ethanol furnished an analytical sample of m.p. 131°. A mixed m.p. with bornyl chloride was the same. Bornyl chloride amounted to 30% of solid (F).

Camphene.—Instead of separating camphene from bornyl chloride, solid (F) (1.5 g.) was oxidised to camphor following the method of Acharya and Wheeler⁹. About 1g. of solids, smelling strongly of camphor, was obtained. A portion of this after repeated recrystallisation from aqueous ethanol failed to furnish an analytical sample of constant m.p. The crude material (200mg.) was therefore directly converted into 2, 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (yield about 280 mg.), m.p. 164°. This m.p. was unchanged when admixed with the 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of camphor, obtained by oxidation of camphene.

Reaction IV. α -Pinene and Chloranil

Oil A.—The fractionation of the oil (22g.) at 739mm gave the following c. ts.: (1) 154-55°: 67.5%, n_D^{20} 1.4660; (2) 156-58°: 7.5%, n_D^{20} 1.4708; (3) 159-63°: 5%, n_D^{20} 1.4796; (4) 163-64°: 7.5%, n_D^{20} 1.4783; (5) 5%, viscous oil.

25. Mirov, *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc.*, 1951, 40, 410.

26. ~~...~~ and Mulliken, "Identification of Pure Organic Compounds", Order I, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 1957, p. 574.

α-Pinene.—Fraction (1) (850mg.) furnished nitrosochloride in about 100mg. yield, m.p. 125°, undepressed by a mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of (±)-*α*-pinene nitrosochloride. Fraction (2) gave only a few mg. of this derivative and fraction (3), none.

Although fraction (4) had the boiling range of *β*-pinene, attempts to prepare nopinic acid²⁵ met with failure.

Bornyl Chloride.—Oil (E) (8.5g), when processed with H₂SO₄ in a manner described under reaction (III), afforded 2.1g of solids which were purified according to the method of Acharya and Wheeler⁹. The solids, so obtained, after twice recrystallisation from aq. ethanol gave an analytical sample of m.p. 131°; this m.p. was not altered in a mixed m.p. with bornyl chloride. Bornyl chloride constituted 25% of oil (E).

Camphene.—Oil (E) (2.5 g.), on oxidation, as given under reaction (III), yielded 1.3g. of solids. Camphor in this was recognised by conversion of a portion (200 mg.) into 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (yield about 300mg.), m.p. 164°.

Reaction V. Bornyl Chloride and Chloranil

Camphene was found to be present in solid (A) by conversion to camphor as described earlier. From 1.5 g. of solid (A) oxidation afforded 1g. of a camphor-smelling solid. A portion of this (200 mg.) furnished 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of camphor (yield about 250 mg.), m.p. 164°.

Bornyl chloride was estimated in the solid (A) by sulphuric acid treatment and amounted to 51%.

Reaction VI. Camphene and Chloranil

Camphene.—Solids (A—E) were found to be only camphene by recrystallisation of a portion of the material from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 50°, undepressed by admixture with an authentic sample of camphene.

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